

MAKING HIV PREVENTION WORK:

Supporting Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis (PrEP) Use & Adherence in sub-Saharan Africa Methodology Brief

Introduction

Insight 2 implementation conducted a rapid review in response to South to South Learning Network (SSLN) Country Champions seeking to understand “how to increase support for, and adherence to, PrEP?”

This brief provides a summary of the methodology used in the rapid review.

We present the inclusion and exclusion criteria and the step-by-step process of identifying papers that were included in the review. We note the limitations of our review, as well as future areas of research.

The objectives of the review were to:

- 1 **Identify** which interventions improve PrEP adherence, including biomedical tools (e.g., pills, rings, injections), behavioural support (e.g., reminders, counselling), and structural changes (e.g., reducing cost, improving access).
- 2 **Assess** how these interventions are delivered to overcome common barriers to PrEP uptake and continuation, with attention to practical, real-world strategies at each level.
- 3 **Examine** how context shapes effectiveness, considering who is reached, which populations remain underserved, and how setting-specific factors influence outcomes.

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Methods

A search was conducted in January 2025 using key search terms on the PubMed database that included:

1. Inclusion Criteria

- a. **Topic of Interest:** Interventions that increase access to and/or support adherence to PrEP.
- b. **Target Population:** All age groups, with - stratified searches by key population groups – MSM, FSWs, PWIDs, AGYW, ABYM, Institutionalised people, transgender people – All HIV negative**
- c. **Geography:** SSLN countries (Botswana, Cote d'Ivoire/Ivory Coast, Eswatini/Swaziland, Ghana, Kenya, Malawi, Mozambique, Nigeria, Republic of Congo, South Africa, South Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, and Zimbabwe).
- d. **Types of journal articles:** Primary research studies and project or programme evaluations.
- e. **Language:** English.
- f. **Timeframe:** 1 January 2019 - December 31, 2024, specifically focusing on the last 5-6 years since WHO released guidelines on PrEP for HIV prevention.

2. Exclusion Criteria

Studies were excluded if they met any of the following criteria:

- a. Published before 2019.
- b. Not an intervention or programme evaluation (e.g, clinical trials excluded).
- c. Did not focus on adherence to, or support for PrEP.
- d. Did not measure PrEP outcomes.
- e. Included PLHIV or HIV treatment interventions.
- f. Conducted outside the SSLN countries.
- g. Wrong article type, e.g, commentaries, opinion pieces, letters to the editor, protocols, case studies, prevalence papers/ papers on associations.

Search and selection process

A total of 40 papers met the inclusion criteria and were included in the final review. The PRISMA diagram below outlines the stages of the literature search and screening process.

Limitations

The rapid review was restricted to primary papers published in English, which could have excluded other relevant papers from Francophone or Lusophone countries in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). Our review was focused on evidence from the 15 countries that are part of the SSLN (noted above). *There is a diverse group of countries and contexts within SSA, which may limit the generalizability of our results.*

Our review found only a few studies from West African countries as compared to the Eastern and Southern African region. We did not conduct searches amongst 'grey literature', and may have missed information from relevant programme evaluations showing promising practices to support effective use of PrEP products. Lastly, our review did not find many studies that evaluated community-level interventions on PrEP outcomes.

Remaining Knowledge Gaps

As new PrEP options are rolled out, it will be important to:

Build in monitoring and evaluation into PrEP programmes: Assess the effectiveness of PrEP programmes across diverse contexts to fill knowledge gaps.

Evaluate Long-Acting PrEP options: Study uptake, effective use, and acceptability across different populations.

Strengthen qualitative insights: Explore enablers and barriers like personal agency, stigma, and provider attitudes to unpack mechanisms of success or failure.

Assess task-shifting models: Compare cost-effectiveness and outcomes for non-traditional provider-led programmes.

Standardise adherence measurement: Inconsistencies in adherence measurement (self-report versus biomarkers) limit comparability. Adopt standardised, validated adherence metrics.

Additional Information

To access more information on the review, see below

- [Overview Brief](#)
- [Methodology Brief](#)
- [Learning Brief for Programme Implementers](#)
- [Learning Brief for Ministry of Health and National AIDS Commission Officials](#)

The full rapid review slide deck can be accessed [here](#)

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Summary

This rapid review provides a robust and context-specific evidence base on what works to support PrEP use and adherence across SSA.

The methods outlined here ensured a systematic yet pragmatic approach suited to programmatic decision-making.

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Papers Included in the review

The review included 40 peer-reviewed articles published between 2019 and 2025.

1. Beesham I, Jaggernath M, Kriel Y, Hao J, Smith PM, Haberer JE, et al. Longitudinal changes in tenofovir and tenofovir-diphosphate concentrations among pregnant women using oral PrEP for HIV prevention: Findings from Durban, South Africa. *J Acquir Immune Defic Syndr*. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1097/QAI.0000000000003586>
2. Chi BH, Saidi F, Graybill LA, Phanga T, Mollan KR, Amico KR, et al. A Patient-Centered, Combination Intervention to Support Adherence to HIV Pre-exposure Prophylaxis During Pregnancy and Breastfeeding: A Randomized Pilot Study in Malawi. *J Acquir Immune Defic Syndr*. 2024;95:42–51. <https://doi.org/10.1097/QAI.0000000000003309>.
3. Nalukwago GK, Isunju JB, Muwonge T, Katairo T, Bunani N, Semitala F, et al. Adherence to oral HIV pre-exposure prophylaxis among female sex workers in Kampala, Uganda. *Afr Health Sci*. 2021;21:1048–58. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ahs.v21i3.12>.
4. Musinguzi N, Kidoguchi L, Mugo NR, Ngure K, Katabira E, Celum CL, et al. Adherence to recommendations for ART and targeted PrEP use among HIV serodiscordant couples in East Africa: the “PrEP as a bridge to ART” strategy. *BMC Public Health*. 2020;20:1621. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-09712-3>
5. Shapley-Quinn MK, Tenza S, Jensen D, Tauya T, Mampuru L, Etima J, et al. Adolescent Girls and Young Women Overcoming Adherence Challenges with Vaginal and Oral PrEP Use: A Longitudinal Qualitative Study from a Crossover Trial in South Africa, Uganda, and Zimbabwe. *AIDS Behav*. 2024;28:4209–23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10461-024-04503-y>
6. Rousseau E, Katz AWK, O'Rourke S, Bekker LG, Delany-Moretlwe S, Bukusi E, et al. Adolescent girls and young women's PrEP-user journey during an implementation science study in South Africa and Kenya. *PLoS One*. 2021;16:e0258542. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0258542>
7. Sensalire S, Nkolo A, Ssali JN, Muhire M, Muhwezi A, Kadama H. Applying a Three-Tier Approach to Address Gaps in Oral Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis Uptake and Continuity in Uganda: A Mixed Methods Approach. *Glob Health Sci Pract*. 2024;12. <https://doi.org/10.9745/GHSP-D-23-00229>
8. Mwima S, Bogart LM, Musoke W, Mukama SC, Allupo S, Kadama H, et al. Applying implementation science frameworks to understand why fisherfolk continue or discontinue pre-exposure prophylaxis for HIV prevention in Uganda: a qualitative analysis. *BMJ Glob Health*. 2025;10. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2024-017368>
9. Mallayasamy S, Chaturvedula A, Fossler MJ, Sale ME, Hendrix CW, Haberer JE. Assessment of Demographic and Socio-Behavioral Factors on Adherence to HIV Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis Using a Markov Modeling Approach. *Front Pharmacol*. 2019;10:785. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2019.00785>
10. Roberts ST, Hartmann M, Minnis AM, Otticha SO, Browne EN, Montgomery ET, et al. Breaking down relationship barriers to increase PrEP uptake and adherence among adolescent girls and young women in Kenya: safety and preliminary effectiveness results from a pilot cluster-randomized trial. *J Int AIDS Soc*. 2023;26:e26198. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jia2.26198>
11. Celum C, Seidman D, Travill D, Dehlendorf C, Gumedde S, Zewdie K, et al. A decision support tool has similar high PrEP uptake and increases early PrEP persistence in adolescent girls and young women in South Africa: results from a randomized controlled trial. *J Int AIDS Soc*. 2023;26:e26154. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jia2.26154>
12. Kayesu, I., Mayanja, Y., Nakirijja, C. et al. Uptake of and adherence to oral pre-exposure prophylaxis among adolescent girls and young women at high risk of HIV-infection in Kampala, Uganda: A qualitative study of experiences, facilitators and barriers. *BMC Women's Health* 22, 440 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-022-02018-z>
13. Shapley-Quinn MK, Tenza S, Jensen D, Tauya T, Mampuru L, Etima J, et al. Adolescent Girls and Young Women Overcoming Adherence Challenges with Vaginal and Oral PrEP Use: A Longitudinal Qualitative Study from a Crossover Trial in South Africa, Uganda, and Zimbabwe. *AIDS Behav*. 2024;28:4209–23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10461-024-04503-y>
14. Bogart, L. M., Musoke, W., Mukama, C. S., Allupo, S., Klein, D. J., Sejjemba, A., Mwima, S., Kadama, H., Mulebeke, R., Pandey, R., Wagner, Z., Mukasa, B., & Wanyenze, R. K. (2024). Enhanced oral Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis (PrEP) implementation for Ugandan fisherfolk: Pilot intervention outcomes. *AIDS and Behavior*, 28(10), 3512–3524. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10461-024-04432-w>

15. Camlin CS, Koss CA, Getahun M, Owino L, Itiakorit H, Akatukwasa C, Maeri I, Bakanoma R, Onyango A, Atwine F, Ayieko J, Kabami J, Mwangwa F, Atukunda M, Owaraganise A, Kwarisiima D, Sang N, Bukusi EA, Kanya MR, Petersen ML, Cohen CR, Charlebois ED, Havlir DV. Understanding Demand for PrEP and Early Experiences of PrEP Use Among Young Adults in Rural Kenya and Uganda: A Qualitative Study. *AIDS Behav.* 2020 Jul;24(7):2149-2162. doi: 10.1007/s10461-020-02780-x. PMID: 31955361; PMCID: PMC7909847.
16. Ddaaki W, Strömdahl S, Yeh PT, Rosen JG, Jackson J, Nakyanjo N, Kagaayi J, Kigozi G, Nakigozi G, Grabowski MK, Chang LW, Reynolds SJ, Nalugoda F, Ekström AM, Kennedy CE. Qualitative Assessment of Barriers and Facilitators of PrEP Use Before and After Rollout of a PrEP Program for Priority Populations in South-central Uganda. *AIDS Behav.* 2021 Nov;25(11):3547-3562. doi: 10.1007/s10461-021-03360-3. Epub 2021 Jul 9. PMID: 34240317; PMCID: PMC8603943.
17. de Vos L, Mudzingwa EK, Fynn L, Atujuna M, Mugore M, Gandhi M, Celum C, Hosek S, Bekker LG, Daniels J, Medina-Marino A. Factors that influence adolescent girls and young women's re-initiation or complete discontinuation from daily oral PrEP use: a qualitative study from Eastern Cape Province, South Africa. *J Int AIDS Soc.* 2023 Sep;26(9):e26175. doi: 10.1002/jia2.26175. PMID: 37758649; PMCID: PMC10533377
18. Fearon E, Phillips A, Mtetwa S, Chabata ST, Mushati P, Cambiano V, Busza J, Napierala S, Hensen B, Baral S, Weir SS, Rice B, Cowan FM, Hargreaves JR. How Can Programs Better Support Female Sex Workers to Avoid HIV Infection in Zimbabwe? A Prevention Cascade Analysis. *J Acquir Immune Defic Syndr.* 2019 May 1;81(1):24-35. doi: 10.1097/QAI.0000000000001980. PMID: 30964804; PMCID: PMC6467580.
19. Gandhi M, Glidden DV, Chakravarty D, Wang G, Biwott C, Mogere P, Maina G, Njeru I, Kiptinness C, Okello P, Spinelli MA, Chatterjee P, Velloza J, Ogello V, Medina-Marino A, Okochi H, Mugo NR, Ngure K. Impact of a point-of-care urine tenofovir assay on adherence to HIV pre-exposure prophylaxis among women in Kenya: a randomised pilot trial. *Lancet HIV.* 2024 Aug;11(8):e522-e530. doi: 10.1016/S2352-3018(24)00125-5. Epub 2024 Jul 5. PMID: 38976993; PMCID: PMC11376217.
20. Felix Sanni O, Umoh P, Kalaiwo A, Abang R, Oguntonade A, Amechi P, Emmanuel G. Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis and HIV Prevention Among Key Populations in Nigeria. *Int J MCH AIDS.* 2024 Jun 28;13:e013. doi: 10.25259/IJMA_6_2023. PMID: 39247140; PMCID: PMC11380895.
21. Gati Mirembe B, Donnell D, Krows M, Zwane Z, Bukusi E, Panchia R, Louw C, Mwelase N, Selepe P, Senne M, Naidoo L, Chihana R, Kasaro M, Nuwagaba-Biribonwoha H, Kotze P, Gill K, MacDonald P, vanHeerden A, Bosman S, Jaggernath M, du Preez P, Ward A, Peters RPH, Delany-Moretlwe S, Peacock S, Johnson R, Caucutt J, Morrison S, Wang G, Gandhi M, Velloza J, Heffron R, Celum C; INSIGHT Study Team. High recent PrEP adherence with point-of-care urine tenofovir testing and adherence counselling among young African women: results from the INSIGHT cohort. *J Int AIDS Soc.* 2024 Dec;27(12):e26389. doi: 10.1002/jia2.26389. PMID: 39653676; PMCID: PMC11628190.
22. Haberer JE, Mugo N, Bukusi EA, Ngure K, Kiptinness C, Oware K, Garrison LE, Musinguzi N, Pyra M, Valenzuela S, Thomas KK, Anderson PL, Thirumurthy H, Baeten JM. Understanding Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis Adherence in Young Women in Kenya. *J Acquir Immune Defic Syndr.* 2022 Mar 1;89(3):251-260. doi: 10.1097/QAI.0000000000002876. PMID: 35147580; PMCID: PMC8826617.]
23. Irungu EM, Mugwanya KK, Mugo NR, Bukusi EA, Donnell D, Odoyo J, Wamoni E, Peacock S, Morton JF, Ngure K, Mugambi M, Mukui I, O'Malley G, Baeten JM; Partners Scale-Up Project Team. Integration of pre-exposure prophylaxis services into public HIV care clinics in Kenya: a pragmatic stepped-wedge randomised trial. *Lancet Glob Health.* 2021 Dec;9(12):e1730-e1739. doi: 10.1016/S2214-109X(21)00391-0. PMID: 34798031; PMCID: PMC8609282.
24. Irungu EM, Odoyo J, Wamoni E, Bukusi EA, Mugo NR, Ngure K, Morton JF, Mugwanya KK, Baeten JM, O'Malley G; Partners Scale-Up Project Team. Process evaluation of PrEP implementation in Kenya: adaptation of practices and contextual modifications in public HIV care clinics. *J Int AIDS Soc.* 2021 Sep;24(9):e25799. doi: 10.1002/jia2.25799. PMID: 34496148; PMCID: PMC8425783.
25. Jackson-Gibson M, Ezema AU, Orero W, Were I, Ohiomoba RO, Mbullo PO, Hirschhorn LR. Facilitators and barriers to HIV pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) uptake through a community-based intervention strategy among adolescent girls and young women in Seme Sub-County, Kisumu, Kenya. *BMC Public Health.* 2021 Jul 1;21(1):1284. doi: 10.1186/s12889-021-11335-1. PMID: 34210288; PMCID: PMC8252310.
26. Joseph Davey DL, Dovel K, Mvududu R, Nyemba D, Mashele N, Bekker LG, Gorbach PM, Coates TJ, Myer L. Pre-exposure Prophylaxis Recent Adherence With Real-Time Adherence Feedback and Partner Human Immunodeficiency Virus Self-Testing: A Pilot Trial Among Postpartum Women. *Open Forum Infect Dis.* 2021 Dec 23;9(2):ofab609. doi: 10.1093/ofid/ofab609. PMID: 35097151; PMCID: PMC8794072.

27. Kawuma, S., Katwesigye, R., Walusaga, H. et al. Determinants of continuation on HIV pre-exposure prophylaxis among female sex workers at a referral hospital in Uganda: a mixed methods study using COM-B model. *BMC Public Health* 25, 143 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-20975-y>.
28. Mansoor LE, Yende-Zuma N, Baxter C, Mngadi KT, Dawood H, Gengiah TN, Samsunder N, Schwartz JL, Doncel GF, Abdool Karim Q. Integrated provision of topical pre-exposure prophylaxis in routine family planning services in South Africa: a non-inferiority randomized controlled trial. *J Int AIDS Soc.* 2019 Sep;22(9):e25381. doi: 10.1002/jia2.25381. PMID: 31507088; PMCID: PMC6737288.
29. Matthews LT, Atukunda EC, Owembabazi M, et al. High PrEP uptake and objective longitudinal adherence among HIV-exposed women with personal or partner plans for pregnancy in rural Uganda: A cohort study. *Plos Medicine.* 2023 Feb;20(2):e1004088. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1004088. PMID: 36795763; PMCID: PMC998383
30. Matthews LT, Bruxvoort KJ, Jaggernath M, Kriel Y, Smith PM, Haberer JE, Bassler J, Bennett K, Psaros C, Bangsberg DR, Hurwitz KW, Smit JA. Use of tenofovir-based preexposure prophylaxis among pregnant women in South Africa. *AIDS.* 2025 Apr 1;39(5):508-518. doi: 10.1097/QAD.0000000000004090. Epub 2024 Dec 20. PMID: 39693489; PMCID: PMC11902610.
31. Mayer CM, Owaraganise A, Kabami J, Kwarisiima D, Koss CA, Charlebois ED, Kanya MR, Petersen ML, Havlir DV, Jewell BL. Distance to clinic is a barrier to PrEP uptake and visit attendance in a community in rural Uganda. *J Int AIDS Soc.* 2019 Apr;22(4):e25276. doi: 10.1002/jia2.25276. PMID: 31037845; PMCID: PMC6488759.
32. Mbotwa CH, Kazaura MR, Moen K, Lichtwarck HO, Leshabari MT, Metta E, Mmbaga EJ. Effect of an mHealth intervention on retention in HIV pre-exposure prophylaxis services among female sex workers: Preliminary evidence of the use of the Jichunge app in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. *Digit Health.* 2023 Apr 20;9:20552076231170507. doi: 10.1177/20552076231170507. PMID: 37113256; PMCID: PMC10126669.
33. Sikazwe I, Musheke M, Chiyenu K, Ngosa B, Pry JM, Mulubwa C, Zimba M, Sakala M, Somwe P, Nyirenda G, Savory T, Bolton-Moore C, Herce ME. Programme science in action: lessons from an observational study of HIV prevention programming for key populations in Lusaka, Zambia. *J Int AIDS Soc.* 2024 Jul;27 Suppl 2(Suppl 2):e26237. doi: 10.1002/jia2.26237. PMID: 38982890; PMCID: PMC11233926.
34. Ojeda VD, Amico KR, Hughes JP, Wilson E, Li M, Holtz TH, Chitwarakorn A, Grant RM, Dye BJ, Bekker LG, Mannheimer S, Marzinke M, Hendrix CW. Low Disclosure of PrEP Nonadherence and HIV-Risk Behaviors Associated With Poor HIV PrEP Adherence in the HPTN 067/ADAPT Study. *J Acquir Immune Defic Syndr.* 2019 Sep 1;82(1):34-40. doi: 10.1097/QAI.0000000000002103. PMID: 31169769; PMCID: PMC6698708.
35. Ogello V, Ngure K, Thuo N, Burns B, Rono B, Oware K, Kiptinness C, Mugo N, Bukusi E, Garrison L, Baeten JM, Haberer JE. "Yes, I'm reminded, but it doesn't mean I'm taking them": Experiences with Short Message Service Reminder Use in Real-time Monitoring of HIV PrEP among Young Women in Kenya. *AIDS Behav.* 2023 Jan;27(1):65-74. doi: 10.1007/s10461-022-03744-z. Epub 2022 Jul 30. PMID: 35907142.
36. Ngure K, Thuo N, Ogello V, Kiptinness C, Kamolloh K, Burns BFO, Mugo NR, Bukusi EA, Garrison L, Baeten JM, Haberer JE. Dynamic Perceived HIV Risk and Sexual Behaviors Among Young Women Enrolled in a PrEP Trial in Kenya: A Qualitative Study. *Front Reprod Health.* 2021 Aug 12;3:637869. doi: 10.3389/frph.2021.637869. PMID: 36304002; PMCID: PMC9580724.
37. Musinguzi N, Ngure K, Bukusi EA, Mugo NR, Baeten JM, Anderson PL, Haberer JE. Performance of Multiple Adherence Measures for pre-exposure Prophylaxis (PrEP) Among Young Women in Kenya. *AIDS Behav.* 2023 Dec;27(12):3961-3969. doi: 10.1007/s10461-023-04111-2. Epub 2023 Jun 23. PMID: 37351684.
38. Musinguzi N, Pyra M, Bukusi EA, Mugo NR, Baeten JM, Haberer JE; MPYA Study Team. Trajectories of Oral PrEP Adherence Among Young Kenyan Women: Implications for Promoting Effective PrEP Use. *AIDS Behav.* 2023 Jan;27(1):171-181. doi: 10.1007/s10461-022-03753-y. Epub 2022 Jul 16. PMID: 35841463.
39. Mujugira A, Karungi B, Nakyanzi A, Bagaya M, Nsubuga R, Sebuliba T, Nampewo O, Naddunga F, Birungi JE, Sapiri O, Nyanzi KR, Bambia F, Muwonge T, Gandhi M, Haberer JE. Peer-Delivered HIV Self-Testing, Sexually Transmitted Infection Self-Sampling, and Pre-exposure Prophylaxis for Transgender Women in Uganda: A Randomized Trial. *J Acquir Immune Defic Syndr.* 2024 Oct 1;97(2):125-132. doi: 10.1097/QAI.0000000000003471. PMID: 39250646; PMCID: PMC11384309.
40. Mugwanya KK, Pintye J, Kinuthia J, Abuna F, Lagat H, Begnel ER, Dettinger JC, John-Stewart G, Baeten JM; PrEP Implementation for Young Women and Adolescents (PriYA) Program. Integrating preexposure prophylaxis delivery in routine family planning clinics: A feasibility programmatic evaluation in Kenya. *PLoS Med.* 2019 Sep 3;16(9):e1002885. doi: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1002885. PMID: 31479452; PMCID: PMC6719826.